

Grain quality

Relation between rice grain quality and land preparation methods

A. Ali, M. A. Karim, L. Ali, S. S. Ali, M. Jamil, G. Hassan, and A. Majid, *Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan*

Several methods of rice land preparation are used in Pakistan depending on availability of irrigation water, soil type, and ease of preparation.

We studied the effect of land preparation methods on grain quality by comparing complete puddling (eight cultivations and eight plankings under 30 d wet conditions); partial puddling (four cultivations and four plankings under dry conditions, and four cultivations and four plankings under 10 d wet conditions); and dry land preparation (eight cultivations

Effect of land preparation methods on grain quality, 1988-90.^a

Quality attribute	Timing of N application		
	Complete puddling	Partial puddling	Dry land preparation
1000-grain weight (g)	19.1 a	18.8 ab	18.2 b
Total milled rice (%)	71.6 a	71.1 a	70.0 b
Head rice (%)	57.0 a	56.2 b	54.7 c
Cooked grain length (mm)	12.4 a	12.2 a	11.8 a
Bursting of cooked grains (%)	6.0 c	7.2 b	9.7 a
Protein content (%)	10.0 a	9.6 a	8.9 b
Amylose content (%)	29.3 a	3.7 a	29.5 a
Alkali spreading value	6.8 a	6.0 a	6.9 a
Gel consistency (mm)	54.0 a	50.0 a	43.0

^a Results were averaged for 1988-90. In a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

and three plankings under dry conditions followed by flooding and transplanting).

We transplanted a medium-grain variety KS282 on the same day of 1988, 1989, and 1990. The experiment was laid out in unreplicated 30- × 60-m plots. Recommended crop management practices were adopted.

Complete puddling produced the highest values for 1,000-grain weight, total and head rice recoveries, cooked

grain length, protein content, and gel consistency, followed by partial puddling and dry land preparation methods (see table). The reverse trend was observed in bursting of cooked grains. The effect of land preparation method on amylose content and alkali spreading value was nonsignificant. The complete puddling produced the highest quality grain followed by partial puddling and dry land preparation methods. □

Rice grain quality as influenced by split application of nitrogenous fertilizer

A. Ali, M. A. Karim, G. Hassan, L. Ali, S. S. Ali, and A. Majid, *Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan*

We studied the effect of split N application on fine-grain strain 4048 during 1989 and 1990 dry seasons. Soil was loamy clay, with pH 8.0, E_Ce 1.95 dS/m, 0.067% N, 10 ppm available P, and 65 ppm available K. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications in a 4- × 9-m plot.

We applied a fertilizer dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. P and K were broadcast and incorporated into the soil during the last puddling. N was applied in two splits (half as basal, half 30 d after transplanting [DT]), or in three splits (one-third basal, at 30 DT, and at 60 DT).

Three splits of N fertilizer produced significantly higher 1,000-grain weight and head rice recovery, and less burst grain during cooking than two splits (see

Effect of split application of N fertilizer on grain quality, 1989 and 1990.^a

Quality characteristic	Timing of N application	
	Basal and 30 DT	Basal, 30, and 60 DT
1,000-grain weight (g)	18.3 b	19.0 a
Total milling recovery (%)	70.2 a	70.7 a
Head rice recovery (%)	48.3 b	53.7 a
Cooked grain length (mm)	14.5 a	15.1 a
Bursting of cooked grains (%)	8.0 a	6.0 b
Protein content (%)	8.7 a	9.0 a
Amylose content (%)	24.8 a	25.0 a
Gel consistency (mm)	61.0 b	64.0 a
Alkali spreading value	4.2 b	4.5 a

^a Results are averaged for 1989 and 1990. In a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

table). Values for gel consistency and alkali spreading were also significantly higher for the three splits but remained in

the same quality groups: soft gel consistency and intermediate gelatinization temperature. □

Pest resistance—diseases

A new symptom of tungro in rice

N. Kobayashi, R. Ikeda, D. A. Vanghan IRRRI; and S. Shigenaga, *Kyoto University Japan*

We tested four accessions of *Oryza glaberrima* a West Africa cultivated rice, for resistance to tungro. The accessions—IRGC 100139, 100153, 102569, and 103437—all showed severe systemic necrosis, a new symptom of tungro infection, 2 or 3 wk after inoculation

(WAI). This is distinct from the usual tungro symptoms of stunting, yellow or yellow-orange discoloration, and reduced tillering observed in susceptible populations of other species.

Fifty 11-d-old seedlings of each accession were inoculated with 10 viruliferous green leafhopper (GLH) adults/seedling for 4 h. We caged another 10 seedlings of each accession with 10

virus-free GLH adults/seedling for 4 h to check whether necrosis resulted from sucking damage by GLH alone.

Seedlings inoculated with viruliferous GLH first showed necrosis at the leaf tips 2 WAI. Necrosis advanced systemically through the seedlings; few survived beyond 3 WAI. Seedlings caged with virus-free GLH did not show any necrosis. Therefore, tungro viruses

caused the necrosis, which is the most severe reaction to tungro we have observed.

We have systematically been screening wild relatives of rice for tungro resistance and have also found systemic necrosis in *O. barthii*, the close wild relative of *O. glaberrima*. This severe systemic necrosis may be species specific. □

Resistance to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) found in wild *Oryza* spp.

N. Kohayashi, R. Ikeda, and D. A. Vaughan, IRRI; and S. Shigenaga, Kyoto University, Japan

We evaluated wild relatives of rice to seek new resistance genes for use in the control of tungro. A partial core collection of 156 accessions, representing the genetic diversity in the genus *Oryza*, was used (Table 1).

Eleven-day-old seedlings were inoculated with viruliferous green leafhopper (GLH) adults at 10 insects/plant for 4 h. Leaves were individually sampled 2-3 wk after inoculation to test for RTBW and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) infection by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Ten of the 12 accessions, which were not infected with RTBV, were tested for antibiosis to GLH (Table 2). Either a 10-d-old seedling or a leaf tip of an adult plant from each accession was placed in a test tube with five GLH nymphs (2d instar). This was replicated 10 times. We graded antibiosis of each accession as high, moderate, or low by counting the surviving GLH nymphs each day for 3 d. The accessions resistant to any virus were determined from the data of more than 10 plants.

In the *O. sativa* complex, *O. nivara* and natural hybrids were resistant to RTSV; but no accession in *O. sativa* complex was resistant to RTBV infection.

The accessions, which were not infected with RTBV, showed a low infection rate with RTSV, except *O.*

longiglumis (IRGC 105146) (Table 2). *O. brachyantha* (IRGC 100115), *O. officinalis* (IRGC 105100, IRGC 105365), and *O. rhizomatis* (IRGC 103421) were not infected by either RTBV or RTSV.

The accessions resistant to RTRV infection showed a high level of antibiosis to GLH. Thus it is difficult to distinguish the resistance to virus infection from the resistance to the vector.

Table 1. Screening wild rices for tungro resistance.

Species	Genome	Tested	Accessions (no.)		
			Resistant to		
			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	FF	5	1	0	4
<i>O. sativa</i> complex					
<i>O. nivara</i>	AA	39	0	0	4
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	AA	6	0	0	0
Natural hybrids	AA	25	0	0	3
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	AA	4	0	0	0
<i>O. barthii</i>	AA	6	0	0	0
<i>A. meridionalis</i>	AA	2	0	0	0
<i>O. ridleyi</i> complex					
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	Tetraploid	3	0	1	0
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Tetraploid	5	0	2	0
<i>O. officinalis</i> complex					
<i>O. officinalis</i>	CC	14	2	2	3
<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	CC	6	1	0	0
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	CC	5	0	0	2
<i>O. malampuzhaensis</i>	BBCC	3	0	0	1
<i>O. minuta</i>	BRCC	12	0	0	5
<i>O. punctata</i>	BB, BBCC	7	0	0	2
<i>O. latifolia</i>	CCDD	5	0	1	1
<i>O. alta</i>	CCDD	3	0	2	0
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	CCDD	2	0	0	0
<i>O. australiensis</i>	EE	4	0	0	2

Table 2. Reaction of RTBV-resistant wild rices to RTSV infection and antibiosis.

Species	IRGC acc. no.	Origin	Plants tested (no.)	Infected with RTSV (%)	Antibiosis to GLH ^b
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	100115	Guinea	29	0	11
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	105146	Indonesia	24	33	11
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	100821	Unknown	11	9	11
	101453	Malaysia	30	3	—
<i>O. officinalis</i>	104672	Malaysia	20	5	H
	105100	Brunei	28	0	H
	105365	Thailand	41	0	H
	105376	Thailand	29	3	M
<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	103421	Sri Lanka	18	0	—
<i>O. latifolia</i>	105139	Guatemala	25	4	H
<i>O. alta</i>	100967	Surinam	19	10	H
	105685	Brazil	29	11	H

^aH = high level of antibiosis, M = moderate level of antibiosis.